

1 **The ubiquitin-proteasome system is associated with regenerative capacity of the spinal cord and**
2 **neurons.**

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7 We studied spinal cord injury and regenerative response potential in the spine using a mammalian model
8 of nerve injury associated with mutation of the Wallerian degeneration process and an axolotl salamander
9 animal model of spinal cord regeneration. At one week post-injury, ubiquitin B and ubiquitin C were both
10 among the genes most dramatically modulated. Uba5 or Uba6 were silenced following injury and in
11 regeneration, as was *Isg20l2*. Psme4 was a target of modulation following injury across setting. We also
12 observed activation of a collection of E2 ubiquitin E2 conjugating enzymes including *UBE2D1*, *UBE2J2*
13 and *UBE2G1* as well as the ubiquitination factor E4B encoded by *UBE4B*. The ubiquitin-proteasome
14 system is associated with regenerative capacity of the spinal cord and neurons.
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